
KINEMATIC MODELING, ANALYSIS, AND REAL-TIME IMPLEMENTATION OF A PLANAR FIVE-BAR PANTOGRAPH ROBOT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the kinematic analysis and real-time implementation of a planar five-bar robot, also known as a pantograph mechanism. Although the mechanism is made from only a few links and joints, its motion is not simple: the same end-effector position can often be reached in different ways, and some configurations can cause loss of control or poor motion quality. For this reason, a usable control system must do more than compute whether a point is reachable. It must also choose the correct motion branch, avoid singular configurations, and keep the robot inside a safe operating region. The paper first develops the position and velocity models of the mechanism in a step-by-step way. It then uses these models to identify the different motion branches, classify the singular configurations, and evaluate the quality of the reachable workspace. Based on this analysis, a verified operating region is defined for safe and reliable motion. The paper also shows how the continuous kinematic model can be implemented in a sampled control loop using only motor encoder measurements. The implementation includes homing, branch selection, reference limiting with virtual walls, comparison of several inverse-kinematics methods, and an estimator for the end-effector position. Numerical results confirm that the proposed implementation keeps the mechanism on the desired branch, avoids unsafe regions, and estimates the end-effector position with accuracy limited mainly by encoder resolution. The paper also extends the main results to the more general asymmetric five-bar mechanism.

Keywords Five-bar robot · Pantograph mechanism · Closed-chain kinematics · Singularity analysis · Workspace analysis · Discrete-time implementation

1 Introduction

A serial manipulator is an open kinematic chain where links are connected one after another, like a human arm, and the end-effector pose is a single-valued function of the joint variables. A parallel manipulator instead connects the moving platform to the fixed base through several independent kinematic chains (“legs”) that close one or more loops [1–3]. Parallel architectures trade workspace volume and analytical convenience for higher stiffness, lower moving mass (the actuators can sit on the base), and better dynamic performance, which is why they dominate high-speed pick-and-place robotics and haptic applications [2, 4].

The planar five-bar linkage, also known as the “pantograph” mechanism, is one of the simplest parallel robots. Despite its simple structure, it exhibits many of the key features of closed-chain mechanisms. Its forward kinematics can have several solutions, it can operate in different working and assembly modes, it has more than one type of singular configuration, and its reachable workspace contains singularities. As a result, the part of the workspace that can

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be used safely for control cannot be determined from reachability alone. It must be identified through a kinematic analysis. The five-bar mechanism is also important in practice (Figure 1). In haptics, it forms the kinematic basis of the Pantograph family of force-feedback devices [5, 6]. The geometry of these devices has been designed using multi-objective dynamic optimization [7], and their design has often emphasized good kinematic conditioning [8]. This paper revisits that design perspective from a modelling point of view. In manufacturing, five-bar robots are used for high-speed planar pick-and-place tasks. Dedicated designs can produce large singularity-free workspaces by taking advantage of the mechanism's mode structure [9], while kinematic calibration across all working modes can improve positioning accuracy [10]. The same architecture has also been used as a mechatronic benchmark platform [11] and, more recently, as the basis for planar devices for upper-limb neuro-rehabilitation [12].

Figure 1: Representative applications of the planar five-bar mechanism.

The kinematics of the five-bar mechanism has therefore been studied extensively. Gosselin and Angeles [13] introduced the classification of singularities for closed-loop mechanisms into two main families. For the symmetric five-bar mechanism, previous work has described the singularity curves, the workspace, and how both depend on the working and assembly modes [14, 15]. Design atlases have also been developed to relate link-length ratios to workspace quality [16]. Closed-form inverse position solutions for the general, asymmetric five-bar mechanism are also well established [17].

Performance is commonly evaluated using manipulability [18] and conditioning-based indices [19]. Merlet [20] pointed out that such indices must be used carefully when the Jacobian mixes quantities with different physical units. This issue is much less severe for the planar five-bar considered here, because it is used only for positioning and its Jacobian has consistent units.

What is less often presented in a single place is the step from this theoretical analysis to a working real-time implementation. In practice, the controller must keep track of the correct kinematic branches, including which of the possible inverse-position solutions and which of the forward-position solutions is being used. It must also handle how these branches interact with the singularity sets and include the numerical safeguards needed in a sampled control loop. The aim of this paper is to make that connection explicit. This paper derives the full kinematic model of the symmetric five-bar mechanism from first principles and shows how the model can be used in a real-time implementation. The main contributions are:

- Closed-form inverse and forward kinematics, with an explicit treatment of the different kinematic branches. These include the working mode of each leg, denoted by ω_i , and the assembly mode, denoted by σ . We also show that $\text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A}) = \sigma$, so that the assembly mode can be tracked directly from the sign of a determinant;
- A velocity model obtained by differentiating the mechanism constraints. This model gives the two Jacobian matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , leads to the Gosselin–Angeles classification of singularities [13], and provides a closed-form damped inverse that remains well behaved near singularities [21–23];
- A workspace and conditioning analysis that defines a verified operating region and keeps the mechanism away from both families of singularities;
- A discrete-time implementation layer that uses only motor encoders. This layer includes homing and branch identification, reference conditioning with virtual walls, a side-by-side comparison of three inverse-kinematics solvers, and a Newton-based estimator for forward kinematics;
- General formulas for the asymmetric five-bar mechanism, with full derivations, collected in [Appendix A](#).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 fixes notation and establishes mobility. Sections 3–4 derive the inverse and forward kinematics, Section 5 the differential kinematics and Jacobians, Section 6 the singularities, and Section 7 the workspace and its conditioning. Section 8 develops the discrete-time implementation, Section 9 reports the numerical verification of the inverse- and forward- kinematics together with the workspace and conditioning maps of the example geometry, and Section 10 concludes.

2 Mechanism description and mobility

The planar five-bar linkage is the simplest non-trivial parallel mechanism. It consists of five rigid bars joined by five revolute joints into a single closed loop. Figure 2 shows the geometry and notation used throughout. Two of the revolute joints are mounted on the fixed base and driven by servomotors and the remaining three joints are passive. The two driven proximal links (length a) carry two passive distal links (length b), which meet at a common point that we call the “end-effector”. The fifth bar is the fixed base segment between the two motors.

We work in a fixed world frame centered between the two motors. The base joints are

$$O_1 = \left(-\frac{d}{2}, 0\right), \quad O_2 = \left(+\frac{d}{2}, 0\right), \quad (1)$$

with d the base separation. The two actuated (input) coordinates are the proximal-link angles q_1, q_2 , measured counter-clockwise from the $+x$ axis. The output coordinate is the end-effector position $\mathbf{X} = [x, y]^T$. Velocities are denoted \dot{q}_i and $\dot{\mathbf{X}} = [\dot{x}, \dot{y}]^T$. A complete nomenclature is given in Table 1.

Figure 2: The planar five-bar mechanism. Base joints O_1, O_2 are actuated (angles q_1, q_2 measured CCW from $+x$); the elbows E_1, E_2 and the apex \mathbf{X} are passive. Proximal links have length a , distal links length b , and the bases are separated by d .

Table 1: Nomenclature.

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	Meaning
a, b	proximal, distal link length	\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}	constraint Jacobians
d	base separation	\mathbf{J}	end-effector Jacobian
O_i	base (motor) joint i	σ	assembly-mode sign ± 1
E_i	elbow (passive) joint i	ϕ_i	distal-link absolute angle
q_i, \dot{q}_i	actuated angle, rate	\mathbf{u}	redundant coordinates
$\mathbf{X}, \dot{\mathbf{X}}$	end-effector pos., vel.	Φ	loop-closure constraint
\mathbf{b}_i	distal-link vector $\mathbf{X} - E_i$	λ	Lagrange multipliers

Before any kinematics, we ask how many independent inputs the mechanism needs. For a planar mechanism the Grübler–Kutzbach criterion [24] gives the mobility

$$M = 3(n - 1) - 2j_1 - j_2, \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of links (including the ground), j_1 the number of one-DOF joints (revolute), and j_2 the number of two-DOF joints. The five-bar has $n = 5$ links and $j_1 = 5$ revolute joints, $j_2 = 0$:

$$M = 3(5 - 1) - 2(5) - 0 = 12 - 10 = 2.$$

The mechanism has **two degrees of freedom**, exactly matched by the two actuators at O_1, O_2 . The robot is therefore non-redundant and fully actuated, and a desired planar position $\mathbf{X} = [x, y]^T$ is generically realizable.

3 Inverse kinematics

We treat inverse kinematics (IK) first because, for parallel robots, it is the more trivial direction, the opposite of the serial case. The problem of the inverse kinematics in this case is:

“Given a desired end-effector position \mathbf{X} , find motor angles (q_1, q_2) .”

The key observation is that each leg is an independent, two-link (2R) serial chain anchored at its own base: leg i must reach \mathbf{X} from O_i using a proximal link a and a distal link b . The two legs do not interact in IK, so the problem splits into two identical 2R sub-problems. For leg i , let $\mathbf{L}_i = \mathbf{X} - O_i$ and $r_i = \|\mathbf{L}_i\|$. A solution exists if the target lies in the annulus reachable by the leg,

$$|a - b| \leq r_i \leq a + b. \quad (3)$$

The law of cosines applied to triangle $\triangle O_i E_i \mathbf{X}$ (sides a, b, r_i) gives the interior angle β_i at O_i between \mathbf{L}_i and the proximal link:

$$\cos \beta_i = \frac{r_i^2 + a^2 - b^2}{2 a r_i}, \quad \beta_i = \arccos(\cdot) \in [0, \pi]. \quad (4)$$

In components, with the target $\mathbf{X} = (x, y)$ and the base pivots $O_1 = (-\frac{d}{2}, 0)$, $O_2 = (+\frac{d}{2}, 0)$, the leg vectors $\mathbf{L}_i = (L_{ix}, L_{iy})$ are $L_{ix} = x - O_{ix} = x \pm \frac{d}{2}$ and $L_{iy} = y$. So, we obtain:

$$L_{1x} = x + \frac{d}{2}, \quad L_{2x} = x - \frac{d}{2}, \quad L_{1y} = L_{2y} = y.$$

Accordingly, the leg's reach is computed by

$$r_i = \sqrt{L_{ix}^2 + L_{iy}^2}. \quad (5)$$

Finally by calculating $\alpha_i = \text{atan2}(L_{iy}, L_{ix})$ the direction of $O_i \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$, the proximal angle is

$$q_i = \alpha_i + \omega_i \beta_i \quad (6)$$

where $\omega_i = \pm 1$ specifies the *working mode* of that leg (elbow on the left or right of the line $O_i \mathbf{X}$).

$$\omega_i = \text{sign}(q_i - \alpha_i(\mathbf{X})) \quad (7)$$

Each leg independently has two solutions, so the five-bar has up to $2 \times 2 = 4$ IK solutions. For the standard apex-up posture described in Figure 3, different solutions resulting in the same end-effector position are shown.

Remark 1. The boundary $r_i = a + b$ (leg straight) and $r_i = |a - b|$ (leg folded) are exactly where $\beta_i \in \{0, \pi\}$ and the two working modes combine. These are *Type-1 singularities*, derived analytically in Section 6.

4 Forward kinematics

Forward kinematics (FK) maps the measured motor angles (q_1, q_2) to the end-effector position \mathbf{X} . For a parallel robot this is the **hard**, multi-valued direction. The problem of the forward kinematics in this case is then formulated as:

“Given motor angles (q_1, q_2) , find the end-effector position \mathbf{X} .”

Geometrically, the whole computation can be reduced to a single idea: *find the point that lies a distance b from each elbow*. Because each proximal link is rigid and directly driven, the elbow positions are single-valued functions of the inputs:

$$E_1 = \left(-\frac{d}{2} + a \cos q_1, a \sin q_1\right), \quad E_2 = \left(+\frac{d}{2} + a \cos q_2, a \sin q_2\right). \quad (8)$$

The apex \mathbf{X} is attached to both distal links, each of length b :

$$\|\mathbf{X} - E_1\| = b, \quad \|\mathbf{X} - E_2\| = b. \quad (9)$$

Figure 3: Inverse-kinematics construction for the apex-up working mode. Each leg is solved independently as a 2R chain: the elbow E_i lies at an intersection of the circle of radius a about the base O_i with the circle of radius b about the target \mathbf{X} (dashed). The orange vector $O_i \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$ defines the reach $r_i = \|\mathbf{X} - O_i\|$ at orientation α_i (green), and the law of cosines gives the interior angle β_i (orange), so that $q_i = \alpha_i \pm \beta_i$ (purple) – here $q_1 = \alpha_1 + \beta_1$ for the left leg and $q_2 = \alpha_2 - \beta_2$ for the right. The $\mp\beta_i$ alternatives are the second working mode of each leg (light blue), which reaches the same end-effector \mathbf{X} with the elbows on the opposite side.

The statement $\|\mathbf{X} - E_1\| = b$ says precisely that \mathbf{X} lies on a *circle of radius b centered at E_1* ; the second statement places it on a circle of radius b centered at E_2 . The apex must satisfy both, so it sits where the two circles cross (Figure 4). Two circles meet at two points in general, and that pair of crossings is exactly where the two FK solutions come from.

Figure 4: Forward kinematics as a two-circle intersection, drawn on the mechanism. The motor angles fix the elbow position vectors \vec{E}_1, \vec{E}_2 , hence the midpoint $\vec{M} = \frac{1}{2}(\vec{E}_1 + \vec{E}_2)$ and the segment vector $\vec{P} = \vec{E}_2 - \vec{E}_1$. The apex lies a distance b from each elbow – i.e. on both radius- b circles (dashed) – and the two crossings are the assembly modes $X(\sigma = \pm 1)$. From \vec{M} one steps the height h along the unit normal \vec{n} (with $\vec{n} \perp \vec{P}$, shown by the right angle) to reach the apex.

Rather than solving two circle equations algebraically, we use a symmetry. Both circles share the same radius b , so every crossing point is equidistant from E_1 and E_2 . A classic fact of plane geometry then applies: the set of points equidistant from two given points is the *perpendicular bisector* of the segment joining them. Both solutions therefore lie on the perpendicular bisector of E_1E_2 , which passes through its midpoint. Let

$$\mathbf{P} = E_2 - E_1 = (P_h, P_v) = \left(d + a(\cos q_2 - \cos q_1), a(\sin q_2 - \sin q_1) \right) \quad (10)$$

and

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2}(E_1 + E_2) = \frac{a}{2} \left(\cos q_1 + \cos q_2, \sin q_1 + \sin q_2 \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\|\mathbf{P}\| = p, \quad (12)$$

The approach is now simply: start at the midpoint \mathbf{M} , then step perpendicular to E_1E_2 by the right amount. Three quantities make this precise – where to start (\mathbf{M}), how far to step (h), and in which direction ($\hat{\mathbf{n}}$). Looking at the right triangle $\triangle E_1\mathbf{M}\mathbf{X}$ in Figure 4. Pythagoras gives

$$\left(\frac{p}{2}\right)^2 + h^2 = b^2 \implies h = \sqrt{b^2 - \frac{p^2}{4}}. \quad (13)$$

With $\mathbf{P} = (P_h, P_v)$ pointing along the elbow segment, rotating it by 90° gives the perpendicular direction $(-P_v, P_h)$; dividing by its length p transforms it into a *unit* vector,

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} = \frac{(-P_v, P_h)}{p}. \quad (14)$$

Multiplying $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ by h then moves us exactly the distance h in that perpendicular direction. Starting at \mathbf{M} and travelling h along $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ we arrive at:

$$\mathbf{X} = \underbrace{\mathbf{M}}_{\text{start}} + \underbrace{\sigma}_{\text{up or down}} \underbrace{h}_{\text{how far}} \underbrace{\frac{(-P_v, P_h)}{p}}_{\hat{\mathbf{n}} \text{ (which way)}}, \quad \sigma = \pm 1. \quad (15)$$

The only remaining symbol is $\sigma = \pm 1$, which chooses the *direction* along the bisector: +1 steps up to the upper crossing (apex above the elbows), -1 steps down to the lower one. Both are genuine solutions at distance b from each elbow; physically the linkage can fold either way. This is the *assembly mode*, shown in Figure 5.

Existence condition. The height $h = \sqrt{b^2 - p^2/4}$ is real only if

$$0 < p \leq 2b. \quad (16)$$

This is common sense: if the elbows are more than $2b$ apart, two links of length b cannot bridge the gap and the circles never meet. When $p = 2b$ exactly, $h = 0$: the circles are tangent, the two solutions merge into one, and the mechanism sits at a Type-2 singularity.

Figure 5: Forward-kinematics ambiguity. The motor angles fix both elbows exactly, but the apex can lie above ($\sigma = +1$) or below ($\sigma = -1$) the elbow segment E_1E_2 – the two assembly modes.

Choosing the branch. Since (q_1, q_2) alone yield two candidate positions, FK requires one additional bit of information – the assembly mode. A clean identity, proved later from the Jacobian (Section 5), settles how to track it. With \mathbf{A} the matrix whose rows are the distal-link vectors $\mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{X} - E_i$,

$$\det \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{b}_1 \times \mathbf{b}_2 = \sigma h D. \quad (17)$$

Because $h \geq 0$ and $D > 0$, $\text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A}) = \sigma$: *the sign of the Jacobian determinant is the assembly mode*, and $|\det \mathbf{A}| = hD$ measures how close the two modes are to merging. As $(\det \mathbf{A})$ is continuous in (q_1, q_2) , σ can flip only by passing through $(\det \mathbf{A} = 0)$. Hence, in practice:

1. **Homing.** Determine σ once at a known reference pose, $\sigma = \text{sign}((E_2 - E_1) \times (\mathbf{X}^* - E_1))$, and store it.
2. **Per cycle.** Evaluate (15) with the stored σ – a closed-form computation, no iteration.
3. **Guarantee.** Confine all motion to the connected, singularity-free workspace cell containing the home pose; then σ is invariant by continuity.

Alternatively, a **single encoder** on one passive (elbow) joint resolves the mode directly and lets \mathbf{X} be read off one leg as a 2R serial chain.

5 Differential kinematics and the Jacobian

5.1 What is a Jacobian?

In one dimension, if the tip position were a function of a single joint, $x = f(q)$, the tip speed would be $\dot{x} = f'(q) \dot{q}$: the derivative f' converts joint speed into tip speed. The Jacobian $\mathbf{J}(q)$ is the multivariable version of that derivative – a matrix that converts the vector of joint rates $\dot{\mathbf{q}} = (\dot{q}_1, \dot{q}_2)$ into the end-effector velocity $\dot{\mathbf{X}} = (\dot{x}, \dot{y})$:

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{J}(q) \dot{\mathbf{q}}. \quad (18)$$

At a given pose, the Jacobian constitutes how fast, and in which direction, the apex moves for a given turn of each motor. The same matrix governs forces by duality, $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{f}$ (a force \mathbf{f} applied at the apex is balanced by joint torques $\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{f}$), and the poses where \mathbf{J} loses rank – where some apex motion becomes impossible – are exactly the singularities of the mechanism.

5.2 Jacobian: Differentiating the constraint, not a direct map

For a serial arm one would simply differentiate the explicit position map $\mathbf{X} = f(\mathbf{q})$ to get $\mathbf{J} = \partial f / \partial \mathbf{q}$. Here that map is the awkward, two-valued forward kinematics of Section 4, so we avoid it altogether. Instead we differentiate the *constraint* the mechanism must satisfy at all times which is the loop-closure equations (9). Differentiating a constraint yields a relation between $\dot{\mathbf{X}}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ rather than an explicit formula; we then rearrange that relation to expose \mathbf{J} .

Each distal link is a rigid bar of fixed length b , so its length cannot change in time. When the two ends of a rigid bar move, the rate at which the bar would lengthen equals the difference of its endpoints' velocity components measured *along* the bar – and that rate must be zero. Writing $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i$ for the unit vector along distal link i ,

$$(\dot{\mathbf{X}} - \dot{E}_i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i = 0 \iff \dot{\mathbf{X}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i = \dot{E}_i \cdot \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i. \quad (19)$$

In other words, the apex \mathbf{X} and the elbow E_i have equal velocity components along the link (Figure 6). This one scalar equation per leg is the entire content of the velocity kinematics.

5.3 Differentiating the loop closure

To formulate that idea, we can differentiate the squared constraint $f_i = \|\mathbf{X} - E_i\|^2 - b^2 = 0$ in time. Squaring removes the square root and keeps everything polynomial.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|\mathbf{X} - E_i\|^2 = 2(\mathbf{X} - E_i) \cdot (\dot{\mathbf{X}} - \dot{E}_i) = 0, \quad (20)$$

which is exactly the rigid-link statement (19) with $\mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{X} - E_i$ (the distal-link vector, of length b). We still need the elbow velocity \dot{E}_i . Because $E_i = O_i + a(\cos q_i, \sin q_i)$ and only q_i varies in time,

$$\dot{E}_i = a \dot{q}_i (-\sin q_i, \cos q_i) : \quad (21)$$

Figure 6: The rigid-link velocity constraint. E_i is an elbow and X the apex of one leg, joined by the rigid distal link of length b . The full endpoint velocities \dot{E}_i and \dot{X} (teal) may differ, but their components *along* the link, v_{\parallel} (orange), must be equal – a fixed-length bar cannot stretch. Equivalently, the relative velocity $\dot{X} - \dot{E}_i$ is perpendicular to \hat{b}_i .

the elbow rides its own circle of radius a , moving tangentially at speed $a\dot{q}_i$. Substituting, and writing $\hat{a}_i = (\cos q_i, \sin q_i)$ for the proximal direction,

$$\mathbf{b}_i \cdot \dot{X} = a \dot{q}_i \mathbf{b}_i \cdot (-\sin q_i, \cos q_i) = a \dot{q}_i (\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i), \quad (22)$$

where the planar cross product $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i = \cos q_i b_{iy} - \sin q_i b_{ix}$ appears because dotting a vector with $(-\sin q_i, \cos q_i)$ is the same as crossing it with $(\cos q_i, \sin q_i)$. Abbreviating $k_i = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i$, each leg contributes the single scalar equation $\mathbf{b}_i \cdot \dot{X} = a k_i \dot{q}_i$.

5.4 The two Jacobians

Stacking the two leg equations ($i = 1, 2$) in matrix form gives the implicit velocity relation

$$\boxed{\mathbf{A} \dot{X} = \mathbf{B} \dot{q}} \quad (23)$$

with

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^T \\ \mathbf{b}_2^T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{1x} & b_{1y} \\ b_{2x} & b_{2y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = a \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad k_i = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i. \quad (24)$$

Two matrices appear, not one – the hallmark of a parallel mechanism. The left matrix \mathbf{A} has the distal-link vectors as its rows, so $\mathbf{A}\dot{X}$ reads off the component of the apex velocity *along* each distal link: it is the pair of rigid-link constraints (19) written together. The right matrix \mathbf{B} is diagonal because each motor drives only its own leg. The legs interact solely through the shared apex, which is exactly what \mathbf{A} couples. \mathbf{A} is the *direct* (or parallel) Jacobian and \mathbf{B} the *inverse* (or serial) Jacobian.

5.5 The end-effector Jacobian

Whenever \mathbf{A} is invertible we solve for the apex velocity:

$$\dot{X} = \mathbf{J} \dot{q}, \quad \mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B}. \quad (25)$$

Carrying out the 2×2 inversion and writing each distal link by its orientation $\mathbf{b}_i = b(\cos \phi_i, \sin \phi_i)$ – so that $\det \mathbf{A} = b^2 \sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1)$ and $k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i)$ – collapses everything to the compact closed form

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{a}{\sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1)} \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \sin \phi_2 & -\sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \sin \phi_1 \\ -\sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \cos \phi_2 & \sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \cos \phi_1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

Each column of \mathbf{J} has a clean physical meaning: column j is the apex velocity produced by turning motor j alone, with the other motor locked. With motor 2 locked, E_2 is fixed and the apex can only swing on the circle of radius b about E_2 , so its velocity must be tangent to that circle – perpendicular to distal link 2. Indeed column 1 of (26) is proportional to $(\sin \phi_2, -\cos \phi_2)$, exactly the direction perpendicular to \hat{b}_2 ; likewise column 2 is perpendicular to \hat{b}_1 . The actual apex velocity is the sum of these two single-motor contributions.

5.6 The Jacobian inverse

For control one usually needs the opposite map – the joint rates that achieve a desired apex velocity, $\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^{-1} \dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{X}}$. Because \mathbf{B} is diagonal this inverse is immediate (no 2×2 inversion needed): each row is just \mathbf{b}_i^\top rescaled,

$$\mathbf{J}^{-1} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{a} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\cos \phi_1}{\sin(\phi_1 - q_1)} & \frac{\sin \phi_1}{\sin(\phi_1 - q_1)} \\ \frac{\cos \phi_2}{\sin(\phi_2 - q_2)} & \frac{\sin \phi_2}{\sin(\phi_2 - q_2)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

Note the symmetry between the two Jacobians: \mathbf{J}^{-1} diverges exactly where \mathbf{B} degenerates ($k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i) = 0$, a Type-1 singularity), while \mathbf{J} itself diverges where \mathbf{A} degenerates ($\det \mathbf{A} = 0$, Type-2) – the two singularity families derived next.

5.7 The damped (singularity-robust) Jacobian inverse

The exact inverse of the previous subsection has unbounded gain: as a Type-1 posture is approached, $k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i) \rightarrow 0$ and the corresponding row of \mathbf{J}^{-1} diverges, so an innocuous commanded velocity $\dot{\mathbf{X}}_d$ – or mere sensor noise mapped through \mathbf{J}^{-1} – produces unbounded joint rates. Whenever a velocity command must be computed *near* the singular sets, the exact inverse is therefore replaced by the *damped least-squares* (DLS, or singularity-robust) inverse [21, 22],

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d, \quad \mathbf{J}^\dagger = \mathbf{J}^\top (\mathbf{J} \mathbf{J}^\top + \mu^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1} = (\mathbf{J}^\top \mathbf{J} + \mu^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{J}^\top, \quad \mu \geq 0. \quad (28)$$

The two expressions are algebraically identical; the first inverts in task space, the second in joint space. The damped inverse is the unique minimiser of a regularised tracking problem,

$$\mathbf{J}^\dagger \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d = \arg \min_{\mathbf{v}} \|\mathbf{J} \mathbf{v} - \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d\|^2 + \mu^2 \|\mathbf{v}\|^2, \quad (29)$$

which states the trade-off explicitly: tracking accuracy is exchanged for bounded joint velocity, with $\mu = 0$ recovering the exact inverse. The behavior is most transparent in the singular value decomposition $\mathbf{J} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \sigma_i \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{v}_i^\top$:

$$\mathbf{J}^\dagger = \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_i^2 + \mu^2} \mathbf{v}_i \mathbf{u}_i^\top, \quad \frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_i^2 + \mu^2} \leq \frac{1}{2\mu} \text{ for all } \sigma_i. \quad (30)$$

For well-conditioned directions ($\sigma_i \gg \mu$) the gain $\sigma_i/(\sigma_i^2 + \mu^2) \approx 1/\sigma_i$ is essentially exact; for degenerating directions ($\sigma_i \ll \mu$) it rolls off as $\sigma_i/\mu^2 \rightarrow 0$ instead of diverging; the worst-case gain $1/(2\mu)$ occurs at $\sigma_i = \mu$. The price is the residual

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}}_d - \mathbf{J} \mathbf{J}^\dagger \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d = \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\mu^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \mu^2} (\mathbf{u}_i^\top \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d) \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (31)$$

of relative size μ^2/σ_i^2 per direction: negligible away from the singular sets and bounded near them. Since a constant μ taxes accuracy everywhere, the damping is in practice *scheduled*: $\mu = 0$ inside the certified operating region of Section 7, ramping up continuously – e.g. $\mu^2 = \mu_{\max}^2 (1 - (\sigma_{\min}/\varsigma)^2)$ for $\sigma_{\min} < \varsigma$ – only when the smallest singular value falls below a threshold [23].

For the five-bar the two singular families act on \mathbf{J} in opposite ways, and the damped inverse addresses exactly one of them. At a *Type-1* posture $\det \mathbf{B} \rightarrow 0$, hence $\sigma_{\min}(\mathbf{J}) \rightarrow 0$ and \mathbf{J}^{-1} diverges: this is the case (28) regularises. At a *Type-2* posture, by contrast, $\det \mathbf{A} \rightarrow 0$ makes $\sigma_{\max}(\mathbf{J}) \rightarrow \infty$: $\mathbf{J}^{-1} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A}$ remains bounded (it merely loses rank), and no damping of the inverse can restore the control authority that the mechanism itself has lost; the protection there is planning – the conditioning floor of Section 7 – together with the damped *forward*-kinematics update of Section 8. The scalar damped updates used by the discrete-time solvers, $\Delta q_i = a k_i c_i / ((a k_i)^2 + \mu^2)$ and its forward-kinematics mirror, are precisely (28) specialised to the 1×1 and \mathbf{A} cases, so a single damping policy governs the entire implementation layer.

6 Singularity analysis

Because a parallel mechanism has two Jacobians, it has two distinct families of singularity (the Gosselin–Angeles classification).

Type 1 — Serial / boundary. $\det \mathbf{B} = 0$:

$$\det \mathbf{B} = a^2 b^2 \sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \sin(\phi_2 - q_2) = 0. \quad (32)$$

This occurs when, for either leg, the proximal and distal links are *collinear* ($\phi_i = q_i$ or $\phi_i = q_i + \pi$): the leg is fully stretched or folded, and the apex is on the boundary of that leg's reachable annulus (3). The robot *loses* a degree of freedom (some Cartesian velocities become unattainable); \mathbf{J} drops rank but stays finite.

Type 2 — Parallel / interior. $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$:

$$\det \mathbf{A} = b^2 \sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1) = 0. \quad (33)$$

This occurs when the two *distal* links become collinear ($\phi_1 = \phi_2 \bmod \pi$), i.e. $p = 2b$ and $h = 0$ in (15). The end-effector can move instantaneously even with both motors locked: the mechanism *gains* an uncontrollable DOF and cannot resist certain external forces. Since $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}$, here $\|\mathbf{J}\| \rightarrow \infty$. These singularities lie *inside* the workspace, which makes them the principal design and control concern.

Type 3 — combined. $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$ and $\det \mathbf{B} = 0$ simultaneously: degenerate architecture poses (e.g. the whole linkage flattened). For a generic five-bar these are isolated points.

Table 2: Singularity types of the five-bar mechanism.

Type	Condition	Geometry	Effect
1	$\det \mathbf{B} = 0$	a leg's a, b collinear	boundary, <i>lose</i> DOF, \mathbf{J} drops rank
2	$\det \mathbf{A} = 0$	two b links collinear	interior, <i>gain</i> DOF, $\ \mathbf{J}\ \rightarrow \infty$
3	both	fully degenerate pose	local loss of control

Figure 7: The two operative singularity types of a five-bar linkage.

The special case $a = b$. When the proximal and distal links are equal, the inner radius $|a - b|$ of the reachable annulus (3) collapses to zero: each leg reaches a *full disk* of radius $2a$, eliminating the dead zone around each base. The folded Type-1 configuration ($\phi_i = q_i + \pi$) then places the apex exactly on the base, $\mathbf{X} = O_i + (a - b)\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i = O_i$. The Jacobian *formulas* are unchanged – a enters only as an overall scale – so $a = b$ is not itself a singularity; it merely enlarges the workspace and relocates the folded singular locus onto the base point.

7 Workspace and conditioning

7.1 Reachable workspace

The reachable workspace is the set of end-effector positions \mathbf{X} for which both legs have an inverse-kinematics solution. Geometrically, it is the intersection of two annuli, defined in (3), centered at O_1 and O_2 . The outer boundary of each annulus, $r_i = a + b$, corresponds to a Type-1 stretched singularity. The inner boundary, $r_i = |a - b|$, corresponds to a Type-1 folded singularity. The reachable region is also divided internally by the Type-2 singularity curve, defined by $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$. This curve separates the workspace into different cells, each associated with one assembly mode. For some example parameters, Figure 8a shows the apex-up cell together with its Type-2 boundary.

7.2 Conditioning and manipulability

Performance varies across the workspace. The manipulability $w(q) = \sqrt{\det(\mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^T)}$ describes how much end-effector velocity can be produced from bounded joint velocities. It becomes zero at singular configurations. The condition number $\kappa(\mathbf{J}) = \sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$, defined as the ratio of the largest to the smallest singular value of \mathbf{J} , measures how uniformly the mechanism responds in different directions. When $\kappa = 1$, the mechanism is isotropic, meaning that it responds equally well in all directions. As the mechanism approaches a singularity, κ tends to infinity. A practical operating region can therefore be defined as a connected part of the workspace where the inverse condition number $1/\kappa(\mathbf{J})$ remains above a chosen threshold. This single condition keeps trajectories away from both Type-1 and Type-2 singularities. Figure 8b shows the map of $1/\kappa$ over the workspace.

8 Discrete-time implementation of kinematics

A sampled-data controller evaluates the kinematics once per control period Δt , at the instants $t_k = k \Delta t$. *Inverse Kinematics* must produce the joint references $(\mathbf{q}[k], \dot{\mathbf{q}}[k])$ from the task reference $(\mathbf{X}_d[k], \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d[k])$ at each step. On the other hand, *Forward Kinematics* must produce the task-space state $(\mathbf{X}[k], \dot{\mathbf{X}}[k])$ from the motor measurements $(\mathbf{q}[k], \dot{\mathbf{q}}[k])$. The only sensing assumed is the two motor encoders; the passive joints ϕ_1, ϕ_2 are not instrumented. Two principles organize everything below. First, *velocity is never iterated*: once the position-level problem is solved, the rates follow exactly from the Jacobian relation $\mathbf{A}\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{B}\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ of Section 5. Second, *branches are decided once*: the working and assembly modes are identified at start-up and preserved thereafter by continuity, never re-decided sample by sample.

8.1 Start-up: homing and Reference conditioning

At power-up the encoders supply the actual configuration \mathbf{q}_0 . The assembly mode $\sigma_0 \in \{\pm 1\}$ is not measured but *known*: it is fixed when the linkage is assembled and cannot change during operation, because a mode change requires passing through a Type-2 posture (Section 6), which the operating region excludes. Homing therefore consists of one closed-form forward-kinematics evaluation and two sign reads:

1. compute $\mathbf{X}_0 \leftarrow \text{CLOSEDFORMFK}(\mathbf{q}_0, \sigma_0)$ by Section 4; consistency may be verified afterwards via $\sigma_0 = \text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A})$;
2. working modes of the legs, for use by the closed-form IK: $\omega_i = \text{sign}(q_{0,i} - \alpha_i(\mathbf{X}_0))$, the difference wrapped to $(-\pi, \pi]$, where α_i is the aim angle of Section 5 (leg straight, $\beta_i = 0$, is excluded by the same operating region);
3. seeds for the iterative solvers: $\mathbf{q}_* \leftarrow \mathbf{q}_0, \mathbf{X}_* \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_0$.

No further branch logic appears anywhere in the per-sample algorithms.

A Cartesian point has no assembly mode as the posture does. Most of the workspace is visited by both modes through different working modes: $\sigma = -1$ or $\sigma = +1$. What operating at fixed σ_0 confines the robot to is the connected cell of postures reachable from home without crossing a type-2 singularity. The same scalar serves both roles: the *sign* of $\det \mathbf{A}$ is the assembly-mode bookkeeping, while its *magnitude* (equivalently $1/\kappa$) is the proximity monitor for the boundary of the cell. The choice of σ_0 itself is therefore a once-at-assembly *design* decision, not a control one.

Before any IK is attempted, the reference is projected onto an admissible set

$$\mathcal{C} = \underbrace{\mathcal{W}_{\text{reach}} \cap \{1/\kappa(\mathbf{J}) \geq \kappa_0\}}_{\text{operating region, Fig. 8b}} \cap \underbrace{\{\hat{\mathbf{n}}_j^T \mathbf{X} \leq c_j\}}_{\text{user walls}}, \quad \mathbf{X}_d[k] \leftarrow \Pi_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathbf{X}_d[k]), \quad (34)$$

where $\Pi_{\mathcal{C}}$ is the Euclidean projection. For half-plane walls such as $y \geq y_{\min}$ the projection is a clamp, $y \leftarrow \max(y, y_{\min})$; for the reachability annuli it is a radial clamp toward the offending base O_i .

8.2 Inverse kinematics algorithm

All variants share the per-sample pipeline of Algorithm 1: condition the reference, solve the position-level problem by one of three interchangeable routines (Algorithms 2–4), evaluate the Jacobians at the converged configuration, and return the exact feed-forward rate $\dot{\mathbf{q}}[k] = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d[k]$. The variants differ only in how the position is obtained.

Algorithm 1 Discrete-time inverse kinematics: per-sample pipeline

Require: Trajectory samples $\mathbf{X}_d[k], \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d[k], k = 0, \dots, K - 1$; geometry a, b, d ; admissible set \mathcal{C}
Require: Homing data $\mathbf{q}_* \leftarrow \mathbf{q}_0, \omega_1, \omega_2$ (Sec. 8.1); tolerance ε ; max. iterations N_{\max} ; damping $\mu \geq 0$
Ensure: Joint references $\mathbf{q}[k], \dot{\mathbf{q}}[k], k = 0, \dots, K - 1$

- 1: **for** $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
- 2: $\mathbf{X}_d[k] \leftarrow \Pi_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathbf{X}_d[k]);$ \triangleright workspace limits
- 3: $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \text{POSITIONSOLVE}(\mathbf{X}_d[k], \mathbf{q}_*)$ \triangleright variant (a), (b), or (c)
- 4: $\mathbf{q}[k] \leftarrow \mathbf{q}; (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \leftarrow \text{JACOBIANS}(\mathbf{q}[k])$ \triangleright at the converged configuration
- 5: $\dot{\mathbf{q}}[k] \leftarrow \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{X}}_d[k]$ \triangleright exact feed-forward rate
- 6: $\mathbf{q}_* \leftarrow \mathbf{q}[k]$ \triangleright seed next sample
- 7: **return** $\mathbf{q}[k], \dot{\mathbf{q}}[k]$
- 8: **end for**

Variant (a): closed form with continuity guard. Each sample is solved exactly by (6), $q_i = \alpha_i + \omega_i \beta_i$, with the homed mode signs ω_i frozen. Two guards are mandatory in floating point: the arccos argument is clamped to $[-1, 1]$ (rounding pushes it outside at the reach boundary, where the derivative of arccos is unbounded), and a continuity test $|q_i - q_{*,i}| \leq \delta_q$ rejects the rare sample on which numerical noise near a Type-1 posture ($\beta_i \approx 0$) would flip the branch; δ_q is chosen just above the largest legitimate per-sample joint motion, $\delta_q \gtrsim \dot{q}_{\max} \Delta t$.

Algorithm 2 POSITIONSOLVE: Variant (a)

- 1: **function** POSITIONSOLVE($\mathbf{X}_d, \mathbf{q}_*$) \triangleright closed form, guarded
- 2: $\mathbf{L}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_d - \mathbf{O}_i, r_i \leftarrow \|\mathbf{L}_i\|, \alpha_i \leftarrow \text{atan2}(L_{iy}, L_{ix}) \quad (i = 1, 2)$
- 3: $\beta_i \leftarrow \arccos\left(\text{clamp}\left(\frac{r_i^2 + a^2 - b^2}{2ar_i}; -1, 1\right)\right)$ \triangleright clamp: boundary rounding
- 4: $q_i \leftarrow \alpha_i + \omega_i \beta_i$ \triangleright homed mode signs ω_i , Sec. 8.1
- 5: **if** $\max_i |q_i - q_{*,i}| > \delta_q$ **then**
- 6: **return** \mathbf{q}_* , raise flag \triangleright continuity guard near Type-1
- 7: **end if**
- 8: **return** \mathbf{q}
- 9: **end function**

Variant (b): task-space Newton. With the forward map $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{q})$ of Section 4 and its Jacobian $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B}$, the residual $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{X}_d[k] - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{q})$ is driven to zero by

$$\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{e} = \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{e}. \quad (35)$$

As a reminder for the mechanism described in Figure 4, the Jacobians are calculated by:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^\top \\ \mathbf{b}_2^\top \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{1x} & b_{1y} \\ b_{2x} & b_{2y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = a \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

By using $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B}$, we get

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{a}{\sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1)} \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \sin \phi_2 & -\sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \sin \phi_1 \\ -\sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \cos \phi_2 & \sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \cos \phi_1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

where

$$\mathbf{b}_i = b(\cos \phi_i, \sin \phi_i), \quad k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i) \quad \text{with} \quad \phi_i = \text{atan2}(y - E_{iy}, x - E_{ix})$$

The end-effector pose is $\mathbf{X} = (x, y)$ and E_{iy}, E_{ix} are obtained from equation (8). Note that the undamped update inverts only the diagonal \mathbf{B} ; it is the damped form $\mathbf{J}^\dagger \mathbf{e}$, and the embedded forward-kinematics evaluation itself, that touch \mathbf{A}^{-1} and therefore inherit Type-2 sensitivity. Each iteration costs one closed-form FK plus one 2×2 product. Near a Type-2 singularity \mathbf{A} is ill-conditioned; replacing \mathbf{J}^{-1} by the damped least-squares inverse defined below bounds the update at the cost of a small steady error:

$$\mathbf{J}^\dagger = \mathbf{J}^\top (\mathbf{J} \mathbf{J}^\top + \mu^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1} \quad (36)$$

Algorithm 3 POSITIONSOLVE: Variant (b)**Require:** Tolerance ε ; max. iterations N_{\max} ; damping $\mu \geq 0$

```

1: function POSITIONSOLVE( $\mathbf{X}_d, \mathbf{q}_*$ ) ▷ task-space Newton
2:    $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q}_*$ 
3:   for  $j = 1, \dots, N_{\max}$  do
4:      $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow \text{CLOSEDFORMFK}(\mathbf{q}, \sigma_0)$ ;  $\mathbf{e} \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_d - \mathbf{X}$ 
5:     if  $\|\mathbf{e}\| \leq \varepsilon$  then
6:       break
7:     end if
8:      $(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \leftarrow \text{JACOBIANS}(\mathbf{q})$ 
9:      $\Delta \mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{J}^{-1} \mathbf{e}$  ▷  $\mathbf{J}^{-1} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A}$ , damped:  $\mathbf{J}^\dagger = \mathbf{J}^\top (\mathbf{J} \mathbf{J}^\top + \mu^2 \mathbf{I})^{-1}$ 
10:     $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q} + \Delta \mathbf{q}$ 
11:  end for
12:  return  $\mathbf{q}$ 
13: end function

```

Variant (c): per-leg constraint Newton (FK-free). The residual is posed directly on the leg-length constraints,

$$c_i(q_i) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\|\mathbf{X}_d[k] - E_i(q_i)\|^2 - b^2 \right), \quad \frac{dc_i}{dq_i} = -a k_i, \quad k_i = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i, \quad (37)$$

with $\mathbf{b}_i = \mathbf{X}_d[k] - E_i$. The two equations decouple and the stacked Jacobian is the diagonal $-\mathbf{B}$ so the (damped) Newton update is a pair of scalar operations,

$$\Delta q_i = \frac{a k_i}{(a k_i)^2 + \mu^2} c_i, \quad \mu = 0 : \Delta q_i = \frac{c_i}{a k_i}, \quad (38)$$

with

$$\mathbf{b}_i = b(\cos \phi_i, \sin \phi_i), \quad k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i) \quad \text{with} \quad \phi_i = \text{atan2}(y - E_{iy}, x - E_{ix})$$

No forward kinematics is evaluated and no assembly mode appears anywhere; the only divisions are by ak_i , so the iteration degrades only at Type-1 postures which is exactly where the IK problem itself loses solutions.**Algorithm 4** POSITIONSOLVE: Variant (c)**Require:** Tolerance ε ; max. iterations N_{\max} ; damping $\mu \geq 0$

```

1: function POSITIONSOLVE( $\mathbf{X}_d, \mathbf{q}_*$ ) ▷ per-leg Newton, FK-free
2:    $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q}_*$ 
3:   for  $j = 1, \dots, N_{\max}$  do
4:      $E_i \leftarrow O_i + a(\cos q_i, \sin q_i)$ ,  $\mathbf{b}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_d - E_i$  ( $i = 1, 2$ )
5:      $c_i \leftarrow \frac{1}{2}(\|\mathbf{b}_i\|^2 - b^2)$ ,  $k_i \leftarrow \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i$ 
6:     if  $|c_1| + |c_2| \leq b \varepsilon$  then
7:       break
8:     end if
9:      $\Delta q_i \leftarrow a k_i c_i / ((a k_i)^2 + \mu^2)$  ▷ two scalar updates, (38)
10:     $\mathbf{q} \leftarrow \mathbf{q} + \Delta \mathbf{q}$ 
11:  end for
12:  return  $\mathbf{q}$ 
13: end function

```

Comparison. Variant (a) is exact with deterministic cost, but it is the only one that carries explicit branch state (ω_i , the flip guard) and its arccos is ill-conditioned exactly at the reach boundary. Variant (b) is the generic robotics approach. It works for *any* differentiable forward model but for a parallel machine it drags the forward problem, with its assembly-mode verification and Type-2 singularity sensitivity, into the inverse one. Variant (c) exploits the mechanism's structure: it is the cheapest per iteration, carries no branch state at all, and fails only where the inverse kinematics problem itself is ill-posed (Type-1).**8.3 Forward kinematics**The forward direction estimates the task-space state from the encoders. The closed form of Section 4 would re-select the assembly sign σ at every sample; the Newton form below never selects it at all – after homing, σ_0 survives implicitly

in the warm start. Pose the loop closure as a root-finding problem in \mathbf{X} ,

$$\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{X}) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \|\mathbf{X} - E_1\|^2 - b^2 \\ \|\mathbf{X} - E_2\|^2 - b^2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^\top \\ \mathbf{b}_2^\top \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (39)$$

whose Jacobian is the direct Jacobian of Section 5 – the exact mirror of variant (c), with the roles of \mathbf{q} and \mathbf{X} exchanged. The damped Newton update is

$$\mathbf{X} \leftarrow \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top + \mu^2\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{c}, \quad \mu = 0: \mathbf{X} \leftarrow \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{c}, \quad (40)$$

ill-conditioned only at Type-2 ($\det \mathbf{A} \rightarrow 0$), which is precisely where the forward problem itself degenerates (the two solution branches merge). The velocity is again exact, $\dot{\mathbf{X}}[k] = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}\dot{\mathbf{q}}[k]$, with $\dot{\mathbf{q}}[k]$ from encoder differencing or a velocity observer. Algorithm 5 states the procedure; tolerance and iteration-count guidance carries over unchanged from the inverse case.

Algorithm 5 Discrete-time forward kinematics with end-effector velocity

Require: Motor samples $\mathbf{q}[k], \dot{\mathbf{q}}[k], k = 0, \dots, K - 1$; geometry a, b, d

Require: Homing seed $\mathbf{X}_\star = \mathbf{X}_0$ (Sec. 8.1); tolerance ε ; max. iterations N_{\max} ; damping $\mu \geq 0$

Ensure: End-effector samples $\mathbf{X}[k], \dot{\mathbf{X}}[k], k = 0, \dots, K - 1$

```

1: for  $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$  do
2:    $E_i \leftarrow O_i + a(\cos q_i[k], \sin q_i[k]) \quad (i = 1, 2)$ 
3:    $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow \mathbf{X}_\star$  ▷ warm start; carries  $\sigma_0$ 
4:   for  $j = 1, \dots, N_{\max}$  do
5:      $\mathbf{b}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{X} - E_i \quad (i = 1, 2); \quad \mathbf{c} \leftarrow \frac{1}{2}(\|\mathbf{b}_1\|^2 - b^2, \|\mathbf{b}_2\|^2 - b^2)$ 
6:     if  $|c_1| + |c_2| \leq b\varepsilon$  then
7:       break
8:     end if
9:      $\mathbf{A} \leftarrow [\mathbf{b}_1^\top; \mathbf{b}_2^\top]$ 
10:     $\Delta\mathbf{X} \leftarrow -\mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^\top + \mu^2\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{c}$  ▷  $\mu = 0: -\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{c}$ 
11:     $\mathbf{X} \leftarrow \mathbf{X} + \Delta\mathbf{X}$ 
12:  end for
13:   $\mathbf{X}[k] \leftarrow \mathbf{X}; \quad (\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}) \leftarrow \text{JACOBIANS}(\mathbf{q}[k], \mathbf{X}[k])$ 
14:   $\dot{\mathbf{X}}[k] \leftarrow \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}\dot{\mathbf{q}}[k]$  ▷ exact end-effector velocity
15:   $\mathbf{X}_\star \leftarrow \mathbf{X}[k]$  ▷ seed next sample
16:  return  $\mathbf{X}[k], \dot{\mathbf{X}}[k]$ 
17: end for
```

9 Numerical verification

We instantiate the geometry with the illustrative parameters of Table 3. All discrete-time runs below execute the per-sample pipeline of Section 8 at $\Delta t = 2$ ms with tolerance $\varepsilon = 1$ nm, $N_{\max} = 10$, and the certified region of Section 9.1 ($\kappa_0 = 0.4$, reach margin 5 mm) as the admissible set. The branch labels identified at homing are the working modes $(\omega_1, \omega_2) = (+1, -1)$ – elbows out, leg 1 opening counter-clockwise and leg 2 clockwise – and the assembly mode $\sigma_0 = +1$ (apex up); as Section 8 guarantees, all three remain constant throughout every run below.

Table 3: Example geometric parameters (illustrative).

Quantity	Symbol	Value
proximal length	a	0.20 m
distal length	b	0.25 m
base separation	d	0.20 m

9.1 Workspace and conditioning maps

Figure 8 shows the two maps introduced in Section 7, using the geometry in Table 3. Figure 8a shows the workspace at the position level. The outer boundary is given by the intersection of the two circles $r_i = a + b = 0.45$ m. These

circles correspond to the Type-1 stretched singularities. Around each base there is also an unreachable disk of radius $|a - b| = 0.05$ m, corresponding to the Type-1 folded singularities. Inside these disks, the corresponding leg cannot reach the end-effector point. The reachable workspace is further divided by the Type-2 singularity curve, defined by $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$. This curve occurs when the two distal links are collinear. In the figure, it lies close to the bases and in the region between them. The highlighted cell corresponds to the apex-up assembly mode ($\sigma = +1$).

Two points made earlier can be seen directly from the map. First, this cell is not limited to points above the base line. When both motors point downward, the end-effector can cross $y = 0$ while staying in the same assembly mode. Second, the cell is large. A grid-based area estimate shows that it covers about 94% of the reachable area for which the inverse kinematics has a solution in the standard working modes. Therefore, restricting the robot to one assembly mode, as imposed by the homing procedure in Section 8, removes only a small region near the bases. That region would in any case be unsafe for position control because it lies close to singular configurations.

Figure 8b shows the inverse condition number $1/\kappa(\mathbf{J})$ over the same region. The conditioning is not uniform. A well-conditioned band runs above the bases, while the conditioning rapidly worsens near both singularity families: near the Type-2 curve below and near the stretched Type-1 boundary above. Near the center of this band, $\mathbf{X} \approx (0, 0.30)$ m, which is also the center of the test path used throughout the paper, the value is $1/\kappa \approx 0.63$. This means that the Jacobian is within a factor of about 1.6 of isotropy. A certified operating region can then be defined by thresholding this field, for example by requiring $1/\kappa \geq 0.4$. Since κ grows without bound near both types of singularity, this single threshold keeps the mechanism away from both the reach boundary and the assembly-mode coalescence. If the selected region is connected, the branch labels $(\omega_1, \omega_2, \sigma)$ remain unchanged for any motion that stays inside it.

Figure 8: Workspace and kinematic conditioning for the parameters of Table 3. The inner “holes” near each base are the dead zones of radius $|a - b|$; the bright band is the well-conditioned operating region.

9.2 Kinematic verification

A round-trip test $\mathbf{X} \rightarrow \text{IK} \rightarrow \text{FK} \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$ at $\mathbf{X} = (0.03, 0.30)$ reproduces the position to machine precision ($\sim 10^{-16}$ m), and $\det \mathbf{A} = \sigma h D > 0$ confirms the apex-up mode.

9.3 Inverse Kinematics

Figure 9 compares the three position solvers from Algorithms 2–4. The test path is a circle of radius 0.08 m centered at $(0, 0.30)$ m. This path stays entirely inside the certified operating region, with $1/\kappa(\mathbf{J}) \geq 0.55$ at all points. All three solvers produce the same joint trajectories to plotting accuracy, and none of them reports a warning or failure over the 1500 samples. The only minor differences appear in the position error. The guarded closed-form solver, Algorithm 2, reaches machine precision, with a maximum error of 2.8×10^{-16} m, using one evaluation per sample. The two warm-started Newton solvers, Algorithms 3 and 4, each stop after three loop passes: two correction steps and one convergence check. Their final errors remain below 4×10^{-13} m, which is three orders of magnitude smaller than the requested tolerance. This is the favourable case in which all three solvers behave almost identically, as expected

from the discussion in Section 8. The choice between them is therefore better judged from the more difficult cases considered below.

Figure 9: Solver comparison along a singularity-free circular path (centre $(0, 0.30)$ m, radius 0.08 m, period 3 s, $\Delta t = 2$ ms). Left: reference and executed end-effector path, with one linkage posture sketched; the three solvers are indistinguishable at this scale. Centre: joint trajectories q_1 (solid) and q_2 (dotted), overlaid for the three solvers. Right: per-sample tracking error $\|\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{q}[k]) - \mathbf{X}_d[k]\|$.

9.4 Virtual wall

Figure 10 repeats the circular-path test with the IK solvers. In this test, the allowed workspace is the rectangular box $[-0.12, 0.06] \times [0.20, 0.40]$ m. The right side of the box cuts 20 mm into the commanded circle. At each sample, the projection Π_C limits the reference position to the box, and the feed-forward velocity is adjusted so that it remains tangent to the wall. Therefore, the executed path follows the circle until it reaches the wall, moves along the wall at $x = 0.06$ m, and then returns to the circle when it leaves the constrained region. This comparison highlights an important point. The virtual wall is enforced by the projection before the inverse-kinematics solver is called. As a result, all three solvers receive the same projected reference. This reference is continuous in position, but has velocity discontinuities at wall contact and release. Since the input to the solvers is the same, all three produce the same wall behavior: the executed x coordinate saturates at 0.06 m in every case, and none of the 1500 samples raises a warning or failure flag.

The differences between the solvers are the same as in the nominal circular-path test. The closed-form solver, variant (a), tracks the projected reference at machine precision, with a maximum error of 2.8×10^{-16} m, using one evaluation per sample. The warm-started Newton solvers, variants (b) and (c), remain below 4×10^{-13} m and usually require three loop passes per sample. During contact with the wall, the mean number of loop passes is 3 , because the projected reference moves more slowly and a few samples converge in two passes. The small kinks visible in the Newton error traces occur when the path contacts or leaves the wall. They are caused by the velocity discontinuities of the projected reference, which briefly increase the warm-start residual. These residuals are still handled within the same iteration budget. Thus, hard kinematic virtual walls are independent of the solver: the guarantee that the commanded pose remains inside the box comes from the projection pipeline, not from the specific inverse-kinematics routine used inside it.

9.5 Singularity handling

Figure 11 tests IK solver variant (c) with the protection layer enabled. The test includes one deliberate encounter with each singularity family.

Type-1 singularity, or reach boundary. The commanded circle is centered at $(0.14, 0.34)$ m and has radius 0.10 m. This circle goes beyond the stretched limit of leg 1 by as much as 66 mm. The projection prevents the reference from reaching this singularity by placing it on the safety margin arc $r_1 = a + b - 5$ mm. Near the conditioning limit, the scheduled damping term, with $\mu = 5 \times 10^{-3}$, keeps the per-leg updates bounded as k_1 becomes small. As a result, the executed path slides along the safety arc and then smoothly returns to the circle when the commanded path re-enters the allowed region. The residual stays below the equivalent of 1 nm (9.4×10^{-10} m), and the iteration budget is never exhausted.

Figure 10: Virtual wall, all three solvers, in the format of Figure 9: the reference circle protrudes 20 mm beyond the rectangular admissible box (red), whose right face sits at $x = 0.06$ m. Left: reference and executed end-effector path with one linkage posture sketched; the executed paths of the three solvers coincide, sliding along the wall while the commanded circle is outside. Centre: joint trajectories q_1 (solid) and q_2 (dotted), overlaid for the three solvers. Right: per-sample error against the projected reference; the kinks in the Newton traces mark wall contact and release.

Type-2 singularity, or interior singularity. The commanded path is a vertical segment at $x = 0.02$ m, moving from $y = 0.30$ m down to $y = 0.02$ m and then back up. This raw commanded segment crosses the Type-2 curve, where $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$. Along the raw reference, the determinant monitor would reach $-6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{m}^2$, which would indicate an assembly-mode change through an uncontrollable configuration.

With protection enabled, the mechanism never gets too close to this singularity. The projection redirects the motion along the boundary of the certified operating region. Along the executed path, $\det \mathbf{A}$ never falls below $+4.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{m}^2$, and the executed inverse condition number $1/\kappa(\mathbf{J})$ stays exactly on the chosen floor, $\kappa_0 = 0.4$, during the excursion. The difference between the dashed commanded monitors and the solid executed monitors in Figure 11 shows the effect of the certified operating region. The branch labels remain unchanged not by chance, but because the protected pipeline keeps the motion away from the singular set.

9.6 Forward kinematics from quantized encoders

Finally, Figure 12 tests the Newton forward-kinematics estimator from Algorithm 5. The goal is to reconstruct the task-space state from realistic encoder measurements. The joint trajectory obtained from the IK solver in Section 9.3 is quantized to 2^{16} counts per revolution. This gives an encoder resolution of $\Delta q_{\text{enc}} = 9.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{rad}$, which is representative of the encoders used in precision five-bar devices. Joint velocities are then computed by finite differences. The estimator runs warm-started from the homing pose, with the assembly mode $\sigma_0 = +1$ entering only once, through the closed-form seed $\mathbf{X}_0 = \text{CLOSEDFORMFK}(\mathbf{q}_0, \sigma_0)$.

The average reconstruction error is $8.0 \mu\text{m}$, and the maximum error is $27.8 \mu\text{m}$. At every sample, the error remains below the resolution bound $\|\mathbf{J}\|_2, \Delta q_{\text{enc}}$, whose mean value is $25.8 \mu\text{m}$. This agrees with the tolerance analysis in Section 8. In other words, the estimator is accurate up to the limit set by the encoders themselves, so reducing the numerical tolerance ε below this encoder-level limit would not improve the measured position estimate. The Newton iteration converges in three loop passes per sample and never reaches the iteration limit. Also, $\text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A}) = +1$ at every sample. This confirms that the assembly mode identified during homing remains unchanged throughout the run.

10 Conclusion

This paper developed the full kinematic model of the symmetric planar five-bar mechanism and brought it to a form suitable for real-time implementation. The mobility analysis confirmed that the mechanism has two degrees of freedom and is driven by two actuators. The inverse kinematics separates into two independent 2R problems, giving four possible working-mode solutions. The forward kinematics reduces to the intersection of two circles and gives two possible assembly modes. This assembly-mode ambiguity is resolved by the identity $\text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A}) = \sigma$. By differentiating the loop constraints, we obtained the velocity model $\mathbf{A}\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{B}\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ and the task-space Jacobian $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}$. This also leads to the Gosselin–Angeles singularity classification. Type-1 singularities occur at the workspace boundary, where $\det \mathbf{B} = 0$, and Type-2 singularities occur inside the workspace, where $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$. The workspace and conditioning

Figure 11: Singularity encounters with the protected pipeline (projection Π_C onto the certified region, scheduled damping). Top row, Type-1: the commanded circle exceeds the stretched boundary of leg 1 by up to 66 mm; the executed path saturates on the margin arc $r_1 = a + b - 5$ mm and rejoins the reference smoothly. Bottom row, Type-2: the commanded descent crosses the interior $\det \mathbf{A} = 0$ locus (dashed monitor); the executed motion is deflected along the boundary of the certified region, $\det \mathbf{A}$ never falls below $4.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2$, and $1/\kappa(\mathbf{J})$ is held exactly at the floor $\kappa_0 = 0.4$.

analysis defined a certified operating region. Inside this region, the working-mode and assembly-mode labels remain unchanged. Therefore, all branch choices can be made once during homing, using only motor encoder measurements. Three inverse-kinematics solvers were compared: a guarded closed-form solver, a task-space Newton solver, and an FK-free per-leg Newton solver. The FK-free per-leg Newton solver is the recommended in-loop option because it does not need to store the assembly branch and only loses performance when the inverse kinematics problem itself becomes ill-conditioned. The formulas in the appendix extend the results to the general asymmetric case, removing the symmetry assumption. Overall, the main lesson is that the parallel structure makes inverse kinematics simple but makes forward kinematics and singularities more delicate. This is the opposite of the usual situation for a serial robot arm.

Appendix A General-parameter kinematic formulation

The body of this paper used the symmetric mechanism (proximal lengths $l_1 = l_2 = a$, distal lengths $l_3 = l_4 = b$). This appendix derives the complete kinematic formulas for the general planar five-bar with four distinct link lengths l_1, \dots, l_4 , in the same constraint-based style as the main text. All symmetric results of the main text are recovered by specialization in Section A.6.

A.1 Notation and parameters

Label the moving links $1, \dots, 4$ and the fixed base 5, with parameters listed in Table 4. The ground pivots are $O_1 = (-\frac{d}{2}, 0)$ and $O_2 = (+\frac{d}{2}, 0)$, and the base length is $l_5 = d$. Let $\hat{\mathbf{a}}_i = (\cos q_i, \sin q_i)$ denote the proximal-link directions for $i = 1, 2$, and let $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_j = (\cos \phi_j, \sin \phi_j)$ denote the distal-link directions for $j = 1, 2$. The elbow points are

Figure 12: Forward-kinematics reconstruction from quantized encoders (2^{16} counts per revolution, $\Delta q_{\text{enc}} = 9.6 \times 10^{-5}$ rad), along the trajectory of Figure 9. Left: the quantized joint measurements fed to the estimator. Centre: the end-effector path reconstructed by Algorithm 5, with one linkage posture sketched; at this scale it overlays the true path exactly. Right: reconstruction error against the resolution bound $\|J\|_2 \Delta q_{\text{enc}}$ of Section 8.

$E_1 = O_1 + l_1 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_1$ and $E_2 = O_2 + l_2 \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2$, and the apex is $\mathbf{X} = [x, y]^T$. Leg 1 is the chain $O_1 \rightarrow E_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$, with link lengths (l_1, l_3) . Leg 2 is the chain $O_2 \rightarrow E_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$, with link lengths (l_2, l_4) . Since the two legs may have different lengths, each per-leg quantity used in the main text must be written separately for leg 1 and leg 2.

Table 4: General link parameters (kinematic).

Link	role	from \rightarrow to	length	angle
1	proximal (driven)	$O_1 \rightarrow E_1$	l_1	q_1
2	proximal (driven)	$O_2 \rightarrow E_2$	l_2	q_2
3	distal (passive)	$E_1 \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$	l_3	ϕ_1
4	distal (passive)	$E_2 \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$	l_4	ϕ_2
5	base (fixed)	$O_1 \rightarrow O_2$	$l_5 = d$	—

A.2 Inverse kinematics

For a desired apex position \mathbf{X} , the two legs can be solved separately as two-link planar chains. Define $\mathbf{L}_i = \mathbf{X} - O_i$, $r_i = \|\mathbf{L}_i\|$, and $\alpha_i = \text{atan2}(L_{iy}, L_{ix})$. A solution exists for leg i only if \mathbf{X} is within the range of that leg. Thus,

$$|l_1 - l_3| \leq r_1 \leq l_1 + l_3, \quad |l_2 - l_4| \leq r_2 \leq l_2 + l_4. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

These conditions define two different reachable annuli. Therefore, the total reachable workspace is the intersection of these two annuli and is no longer symmetric about the mid-plane. Using the law of cosines in triangle $\triangle O_i E_i \mathbf{X}$, the angle β_i at O_i is given by

$$\cos \beta_1 = \frac{r_1^2 + l_1^2 - l_3^2}{2 l_1 r_1}, \quad \cos \beta_2 = \frac{r_2^2 + l_2^2 - l_4^2}{2 l_2 r_2}, \quad \beta_i = \arccos(\cdot) \in [0, \pi]. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The actuated joint angles are then

$$q_i = \alpha_i + \omega_i \beta_i, \quad \omega_i = \pm 1, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where ω_i selects the working mode of leg i . It determines on which side of the line $O_i \mathbf{X}$ the elbow lies. Since each leg has two possible working modes, there can be up to $2 \times 2 = 4$ inverse-kinematic solutions. Once q_i is known, the elbow position and the distal link angle are obtained from

$$E_i = O_i + l_i \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i, \quad \phi_i = \text{atan2}(y - E_{iy}, x - E_{ix}). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

For leg i , the two working modes become identical when $\beta_i \in 0, \pi$. This occurs on the boundary circles of (A.1). Figure 13 illustrates the construction. Unlike the symmetric case shown in Figure 3, the construction circles now have four distinct radii, including two different circles centered at the target.

Figure 13: Inverse-kinematics construction for the general mechanism (drawn with $l_1 = 3.0$, $l_2 = 2.4$, $l_3 = 2.6$, $l_4 = 3.2$, in the working modes $\omega = (+1, -1)$). Each leg is solved independently as a 2R chain, exactly as in the symmetric case, but the construction circles now have four distinct radii: the elbow E_1 lies at an intersection of the radius- l_1 circle about O_1 with the *inner* radius- l_3 circle about the target \mathbf{X} , while E_2 uses the radius- l_2 and the *outer* radius- l_4 circles (all dashed). The orange vector $O_i \rightarrow \mathbf{X}$ defines the reach r_i at orientation α_i (green), the law of cosines (A.2) – now with a different expression per leg – gives the interior angle β_i (orange), and $q_i = \alpha_i + \omega_i \beta_i$ (purple) as in (A.3). The $-\omega_i$ alternatives (light blue) are the second working mode of each leg.

A.3 Forward kinematics

Given the actuated angles (q_1, q_2) , the elbow positions from (A.4) are fixed. The apex position \mathbf{X} must then satisfy the two distance constraints

$$\|\mathbf{X} - E_1\| = l_3, \quad \|\mathbf{X} - E_2\| = l_4. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Above equation constitutes that \mathbf{X} must lie on two circles, one centered at E_1 with radius l_3 , and one centered at E_2 with radius l_4 . Let $\mathbf{P} = E_2 - E_1$, $p = \|\mathbf{P}\|$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}} = \mathbf{P}/p$, and let $\hat{\mathbf{n}} = (-P_y, P_x)/p$ be the left-hand unit normal to the elbow chord \mathbf{P} . Subtracting the squared constraints cancels the quadratic terms:

$$\|\mathbf{X} - E_1\|^2 - \|\mathbf{X} - E_2\|^2 = 2\mathbf{P} \cdot (\mathbf{X} - E_1) - p^2 = l_3^2 - l_4^2. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

This gives a linear condition on the position of \mathbf{X} . In particular, the projection $e := (\mathbf{X} - E_1) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{P}}$ of the apex onto the elbow chord is fixed:

$$e = \frac{p^2 + l_3^2 - l_4^2}{2p}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Because the two distal links may have different lengths, this projected point does not generally lie at the midpoint of the chord. It is at the midpoint only when $l_3 = l_4$, in which case $e = p/2$. The remaining distance from the chord is found from Pythagoras, using l_3 as the hypotenuse. This gives the normal offset h and the apex position:

$$h = \sqrt{l_3^2 - e^2}, \quad \boxed{\mathbf{X} = E_1 + e\hat{\mathbf{P}} + \sigma h\hat{\mathbf{n}}, \quad \sigma = \pm 1.} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Here, σ selects which side of the elbow chord the apex lies on. Thus, when both solutions exist, the mechanism has two assembly modes. A real solution exists only when h is real, equivalently when the two circles intersect:

$$|l_3 - l_4| \leq p \leq l_3 + l_4. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The two limiting cases correspond to the two possible circle tangencies. When $p = l_3 + l_4$, the circles touch externally: the distal links are aligned along the chord, and the apex lies between the elbows. When $p = |l_3 - l_4|$, the circles touch internally: the distal links are again collinear, but the shorter one is folded back along the longer one, and the apex lies beyond one elbow. In both tangency cases, $h = 0$. The two assembly modes $\sigma = \pm 1$ then merge, and the mechanism is at a Type-2 singularity. The internal tangency case requires $l_3 \neq l_4$, so it is a purely asymmetric effect. It does not occur in the symmetric mechanism of the main text, where $|l_3 - l_4| = 0$ and this case can only be reached in the degenerate situation where the two elbows coincide.

Figure 14 shows the construction on the mechanism. Compared with the symmetric case in Figure 4, the two dashed circles now have different radii. As a result, the foot of the apex on the elbow chord is the point F given by (A.7), rather than the chord midpoint M .

Figure 14: Forward kinematics of the general mechanism as a two-circle intersection (drawn with $l_1 = 3.0$, $l_2 = 2.4$, $l_3 = 2.6$, $l_4 = 3.2$). The motor angles fix the elbow vectors \vec{E}_1, \vec{E}_2 , hence the chord $\vec{P} = \vec{E}_2 - \vec{E}_1$. The apex lies on the radius- l_3 circle about E_1 and the radius- l_4 circle about E_2 (dashed) – circles of different size, so the foot of the apex is no longer the chord midpoint M (gray): it is the radical-line foot F , at distance $e = (p^2 + l_3^2 - l_4^2)/(2p)$ from E_1 along \hat{P} as in (A.7) ($e = 0.85$ here versus $p/2 = 1.45$). From F one steps the height $h = \sqrt{l_3^2 - e^2}$ along the unit normal \hat{n} (right angle shown) to reach the two assembly modes $X(\sigma = \pm 1)$ of (A.8).

A.4 Velocity Jacobian

Differentiate each constraint of (A.5) in its squared form. With $\mathbf{b}_1 = \mathbf{X} - E_1$ (length l_3), $\mathbf{b}_2 = \mathbf{X} - E_2$ (length l_4), and $\dot{E}_i = l_i \dot{q}_i (-\sin q_i, \cos q_i)$,

$$\mathbf{b}_i \cdot \dot{\mathbf{X}} = l_i k_i \dot{q}_i, \quad k_i = \hat{\mathbf{a}}_i \times \mathbf{b}_i = l_{2+i} \sin(\phi_i - q_i), \quad (\text{A.10})$$

which stack into the implicit velocity relation

$$\mathbf{A} \dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{B} \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1^\top \\ \mathbf{b}_2^\top \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} l_1 k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & l_2 k_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Whenever \mathbf{A} is invertible, $\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{J} \dot{\mathbf{q}}$ with $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{B}$, and carrying out the 2×2 inversion yields the explicit form

$$\mathbf{J} = \frac{1}{\sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1)} \begin{bmatrix} l_1 \sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \sin \phi_2 & -l_2 \sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \sin \phi_1 \\ -l_1 \sin(\phi_1 - q_1) \cos \phi_2 & l_2 \sin(\phi_2 - q_2) \cos \phi_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

together with the inverse map, immediate because \mathbf{B} is diagonal,

$$\mathbf{J}^{-1} = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\cos \phi_1}{l_1 \sin(\phi_1 - q_1)} & \frac{\sin \phi_1}{l_1 \sin(\phi_1 - q_1)} \\ \frac{\cos \phi_2}{l_2 \sin(\phi_2 - q_2)} & \frac{\sin \phi_2}{l_2 \sin(\phi_2 - q_2)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

The determinants carry the geometry:

$$\det \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{b}_1 \times \mathbf{b}_2 = l_3 l_4 \sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1), \quad \det \mathbf{B} = l_1 l_2 k_1 k_2. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Moreover the assembly-mode identity of the main text survives unchanged: substituting $\mathbf{b}_1 = e \hat{P} + \sigma h \hat{n}$ and $\mathbf{b}_2 = (e - p) \hat{P} + \sigma h \hat{n}$ from (A.8) into the cross product gives

$$\det \mathbf{A} = \sigma h [e - (e - p)] (\hat{P} \times \hat{n}) = \sigma h p, \quad \text{hence} \quad \text{sign}(\det \mathbf{A}) = \sigma : \quad (\text{A.15})$$

for any link lengths, the sign of the direct-Jacobian determinant is the assembly mode, and its magnitude hD measures the distance to mode coalescence.

A.5 Singular configurations

The classification from Section 6 also applies to the asymmetric five-bar mechanism. The same singularity types appear, but their locations are changed by the unequal link lengths.

Type-1 ($\det \mathbf{B} = 0$): this case occurs when $k_i = 0$, or equivalently when $\phi_i = q_i \bmod \pi$. In this configuration, leg i is either stretched or folded. In task space, these singularities correspond to the four boundary circles of (A.1). Since the two legs can have different link lengths, these circles now have different radii, and the workspace boundary is formed from arcs of all four circles.

Type-2 ($\det \mathbf{A} = 0$): this case occurs when $\phi_1 = \phi_2 \bmod \pi$, or equivalently when $h = 0$ in (A.8). It is reached on the two tangency branches of (A.9): the stretched branch, $p = l_3 + l_4$, and, only when $l_3 \neq l_4$, the folded branch, $p = |l_3 - l_4|$. Thus, the interior Type-2 locus of an asymmetric design can have more components than in the symmetric case. This directly affects how large a singularity-free cell can be made, and is one of the main trade-offs in five-bar dimensional synthesis [9, 15, 16].

Type-3: this case occurs when both determinants vanish at the same time. For generic link lengths, these configurations are isolated and fully degenerate.

A.6 Symmetric specialization

Setting $l_1 = l_2 = a$ and $l_3 = l_4 = b$ collapses every formula of this appendix onto its main-text counterpart:

$$e = \frac{p}{2}, \quad k_i = b \sin(\phi_i - q_i), \quad \mathbf{B} = a \operatorname{diag}(k_1, k_2), \quad \det \mathbf{A} = b^2 \sin(\phi_2 - \phi_1), \quad (\text{A.16})$$

the two reachable annuli (A.1) coincide, (A.12)–(A.13) reduce to the expressions of Section 5, and the folded Type-2 branch $p = |l_3 - l_4|$ disappears, leaving the single stretched branch $p = 2b$ of the main text.

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